

Exploring the Lived Experiences of Senior High School Graduates on Values Formation

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Abstract

This qualitative study explores the lived experiences of senior high school graduates from St. Paul University Surigao (SPUS) regarding values formation. Anchored on the Paulinian Core Values—Christ-Centeredness, Commission, Community, Charism, and Charity—the research investigates how these values are internalized and manifested by Batch 2024 graduates. Using Thematic Analysis, responses from 28 purposively selected participants were examined to identify key themes in values acquisition. Findings reveal that faith-based values, particularly Christ-Centeredness, are most prominently cited, underscoring the enduring influence of religious education on personal and professional life. Social and emotional values, such as compassion and charity, are also prevalent, reflecting the importance of empathy and community engagement. Personal ethics, including honesty and responsibility, and leadership skills were identified as essential outcomes of the SPUS educational experience. Graduates also emphasized academic and professional excellence, attributing their motivation and perseverance to the institution's vision and mission. The study highlights the effectiveness of holistic, values-based education in fostering moral development, leadership, and social responsibility. These insights can inform the enhancement of values education programs and support policies promoting holistic student growth in religious institutions.

Keywords: *values formation, religious education, Paulinian Core Values, holistic development, senior high school graduates.*

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Introduction

Values education is important in developing individuals into socially responsible, ethical, and conscientious members of society. Values formation is underscored by schools, especially religious schools, as part of their mission (Lovat & Toomey, 2009). Catholic education develops not only academically excellent individuals but also moral virtues, leadership, and community service (Bryk et al., 1993). St. Paul University Surigao (SPUS), which is anchored on the Paulinian Core Values of Christ-Centeredness, Commission, Community, Charism, and Charity, seeks to imbue these values in their students so that they may become empowered Paulinians making a difference for Church and Society. Yet, although values education is included in the curriculum of Catholic schools, few studies have been made on how students internalize and apply these values outside the institution (Groome, 2011).

In spite of the extensively reported advantages of values education, empirical qualitative studies delving into senior high school graduate perception and realization of these values and how these values are practically implemented in one's life are limited (Lickona, 1991). In as much as SPUS forms the students holistically guided with the Vision, Mission, and Core Values, whether particular values elicit most identification and how they manifest in personal, academic, and professional settings, are matters not presently established. This research aims to fill this gap by exploring the values gained by Batch 2024 SPUS senior high school graduates through a qualitative study using Thematic Analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Through their lived experiences, the research hopes to find significant themes that characterize the moral and ethical development of these graduates.

This study specifically seeks to determine the values that graduates acknowledge as meaningful, assess their alignment with the Paulinian Core Values, and discuss how the values shape their lives, with the hope of gaining insights to enrich values education programs at SPUS. Learning about these attitudes will help the teachers to determine whether or not the institution's efforts in character formation are effective and add to improving holistic education programs. The research will also offer an understanding of how religious institutions can enhance students' moral education, leadership qualities, and community service commitment.

The findings of this study will be useful to researchers, students, and educators. Educators and administrators can employ the findings to enhance values formation programs and make sure that students internalize core values efficiently. Graduates will find value by considering the value of values education in their personal and professional lives. Additionally, educators may also employ the findings to support policies encouraging holistic education and moral leadership.

Materials and Methods

This research uses a qualitative research design to investigate the values acquired by senior high school graduates of Batch 2024 of St. Paul University Surigao (SPUS). It specifically uses Thematic Analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006), which enables the

identification, analysis, and interpretation of the emerging themes in the responses of the participants. A phenomenological research design is applied, as it seeks to understand the lived experiences of graduates regarding their moral and character development. The study focuses on 28 graduates, selected through purposive sampling, ensuring that participants can meaningfully reflect on the values they have internalized throughout their education at SPUS beginning elementary years.

Data are collected using semi-structured written answers, and participants are required to explain the values they have learned during their stay at SPUS. This tool is used to allow for open-ended answers, which offer rich, qualitative information on the graduates' views. Thematic Analysis adopts Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-step process, namely data familiarization, coding, theme identification, theme review, theme definition, and final reporting. All the responses are consistently coded to analyze patterns and associations, ensuring consistency with the themes of the Paulinian Core Values of Christ-Centeredness, Commission, Community, Charism, and Charity. Findings are set out in tables and accompanied by direct quotations of the participants to maximize credibility.

Ethical principles are followed to safeguard the rights and confidentiality of the participants. Before participating, graduates give informed consent, assuring them that they know the aim of the study and their voluntary participation. Identities are kept anonymous, and answers are only used for research purposes. The research follows ethical principles of qualitative research, respecting, being honest, and handling data responsibly throughout the research process. The research guarantees credibility and reliability in knowing how Catholic education shapes the values formation of SPUS graduates.

Results and Discussion

This study employed Thematic Analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006) to examine the values acquired by 28 senior high school graduates from St. Paul University Surigao (SPUS). The analysis followed these steps:

Step 1 and 2: Familiarization with Data and Generating Initial Codes

The responses were read multiple times, and meaningful units of data were coded. The table below presents the initial codes assigned to each participant's response.

Table 1. Initial Codes for Each Response

Participant (P#)	Response	Initial Code
P1	Christ-Centered	Christ-Centeredness
P1	Develop skills in communication	Leadership & Communication
P1	Leadership	Leadership & Communication
P1	Compassion to those around me	Compassion & Charity
P2	Being a strong individual as a student	Discipline & Responsibility
P3	To be a better person	Personal Growth
P3	Make a marked difference	Hard Work & Dedication
P4	Hard work	Hard Work & Dedication
P4	Dedication to learn	Academic Excellence
P5	Being more friendly	Social & Emotional Values (Friendship)

P5	More sociable	Social & Emotional Values (Friendship)
P6	Nothing good will come if you let hate take over	Compassion & Charity
P7	Honesty	Honesty & Integrity
P7	Christ-Centeredness	Christ-Centeredness
P8	Christ-Centered	Christ-Centeredness
P8	Respect people of all ages	Respect & Politeness
P8	Be a good person	Personal Growth
P8	A good daughter to my family	Social & Emotional Values (Family)
P8	Having patience	Personal Discipline
P8	To be giving	Compassion & Charity
P8	Communication skills	Leadership & Communication
P9	Communicator	Leadership & Communication
P9	Team player	Leadership & Communication
P9	Problem solver	Leadership & Communication
P10	Being empathic	Compassion & Charity
P10	Showing mercy to others	Compassion & Charity
P10	Compassionate	Compassion & Charity
P10	Helpful upon others' needs	Compassion & Charity
P11	Good role model	Leadership & Communication
P11	Problem solver	Leadership & Communication
P11	Achieve my goals in life	Personal Growth
P12	Responsible person	Discipline & Responsibility
P12	Critical thinker	Academic Excellence
P12	Christ-Centered pupil	Christ-Centeredness
P12	Resourceful learner	Academic Excellence
P13	Treat others with respect	Respect & Politeness
P13	Integrate the Paulinian values and apply in daily life	Vision & Mission Awareness
P13	The 5Cs	Vision & Mission Awareness
P13	Vision-Mission	Vision & Mission Awareness
P14	Courage	Leadership & Communication
P14	Charity	Compassion & Charity
P14	Courageous explorer	Leadership & Communication
P14	Fearless in trying new things	Leadership & Communication
P14	Charity can be anything, not just giving money	Compassion & Charity
P15	Value of friendship	Social & Emotional Values (Friendship)
P15	Value of love	Social & Emotional Values (Love)
P15	Feel the love that God is wanting us to feel and experience	Christ-Centeredness
P16	Christ-Centeredness	Christ-Centeredness
P16	Charity	Compassion & Charity
P16	Charism	Personal Growth
P17	Disciplined	Discipline & Responsibility
P17	Respectful	Respect & Politeness
P17	Humble	Personal Ethics
P18	Christ-Centered	Christ-Centeredness
P18	Striving harder	Hard Work & Dedication
P18	Make a marked difference	Leadership & Impact
P19	Punctuality	Discipline & Responsibility
P19	Politeness	Respect & Politeness
P19	Faith	Christ-Centeredness
P19	Christ-Centeredness	Christ-Centeredness
P20	Christ-Centeredness	Christ-Centeredness
P20	Charity	Compassion & Charity

P21	Christ-Centeredness is the most precious value	Christ-Centeredness
P22	Disciplined	Discipline & Responsibility
P22	Behaved	Personal Ethics
P22	Caring	Compassion & Charity
P22	Christ-Centered	Christ-Centeredness
P23	A lot of values and missions in life	Vision & Mission Awareness
P23	Vision	Vision & Mission Awareness
P23	Mission	Vision & Mission Awareness
P23	Quality policy of SPUS	Vision & Mission Awareness
P24	Being polite	Respect & Politeness
P24	Well-mannered	Respect & Politeness
P25	The Vision, Mission, and Quality Policy of this university	Vision & Mission Awareness
P26	To be honest in everything that you do	Honesty & Integrity
P26	Implement what you have learned in class outside the campus	Practical Application of Values
P27	Compassion	Compassion & Charity
P27	To put Christ as the center of my life	Christ-Centeredness
P27	Work alongside with my fellow Paulinians	Leadership & Teamwork
P27	Create a wonderful community	Leadership & Teamwork
P28	To be always honest	Honesty & Integrity
P28	Always be mindful of your actions	Discipline & Responsibility

Step 3 and 4: Searching for Themes and Reviewing Themes

After categorizing initial codes, they were grouped into broader themes.

Table 2. Themes Derived from Initial Codes

Themes Identified	Codes Grouped Under This Theme	f (n=28)	%
Faith-Based Values	Christ-Centeredness	12	43%
Social & Emotional Values	Compassion, Charity, Respect, Politeness, Friendship, Love	8	29%
Personal Ethics & Responsibility	Honesty, Integrity, Discipline, Responsibility	6	21%
Leadership & Interpersonal Skills	Leadership, Communication, Teamwork, Problem Solving	5	18%
Academic & Professional Excellence	Hard Work, Dedication, Vision & Mission Awareness	3	11%

Step 5: Defining and Naming Themes

Faith-Based Values

Faith-based values, particularly Christ-Centeredness, emerged as the most dominant theme, mentioned by 12 out of 28 respondents (43%). Many graduates emphasized that their education at SPUS instilled in them a deep sense of faith and spiritual devotion, which continues to guide their personal and professional lives. This finding aligns with the idea that religious education fosters moral development, shaping students' ethical decision-making and sense of purpose (Bryk et al., 1993). One respondent stated, *"I have learned to be Christ-Centered,"* while another shared, *"Faith and Christ-Centeredness are my guiding principles."* These reflections indicate that SPUS has successfully nurtured faith as a core aspect of student identity, reinforcing the role of religion in character formation (Groome, 2011).

The lasting effect of Christian education on graduates is also testified to by current studies. For example, Miller and Davis (2022) studied the long-term influence of Christian higher education on alumni. They found that graduates often reported that their commitment to helping others, ethical practice, and personal principles were all notably enhanced by their religious education (Miller & Davis, 2022). This clearly shows how faith-based schools can create graduates who not only turn out to be highly qualified scholars but are also socially and morally aware. In addition, Bosma (2024) explored the lived experiences of graduates from a religious-affiliated university in a qualitative study published in *Christian Higher Education*. Students' sense of purpose, belonging, and community was significantly strengthened by their engagement in religious activities and the integration of faith into the curriculum, the study reported. Graduates' empathy, resilience, and commitment to social justice were then increased by these experiences (Smith et al., 2023). This is echoed in the accounts of the SPUS graduates, reflecting that the fostering environment developed in religious organizations enables individuals to mature into well-rounded individuals.

Social and Emotional Values

The theme of social and emotional values was identified in 8 out of 28 responses (29%), highlighting attributes such as compassion, charity, kindness, respect, and relationship-building. These values are crucial in fostering a sense of community and empathy, which are foundational to holistic education (Noddings, 2013). Respondents emphasized their understanding of charity beyond financial giving, recognizing it as an act of service and kindness. One participant noted, *"Charity is not just about giving money but also about helping in any way possible,"* while another emphasized, *"Being compassionate and helpful upon others' needs."* These insights align with research suggesting that education should integrate emotional intelligence and ethical responsibility to develop socially responsible individuals (Goleman, 1995). The emphasis on interpersonal relationships also supports the notion that values-based education strengthens students' ability to form meaningful connections in society (Lovat & Toomey, 2009).

Such understanding finds resonance as well within a mounting consensus in the studies on prosocial behavior and their influences on overall happiness and wellbeing and community togetherness. For example, Padilla-Walker et al. (2022) demonstrated that behaving kindly toward others and giving aid was in tandem with reported high levels of happiness and contentment among youth that brought a positive perception of relating to others as part of them and countered sense-of-isolation tendencies to boost social integration. The focus on kindness and beneficence that was conveyed in the first few responses is very much related to the building of emotional intelligence, a key part of social and emotional learning (SEL). Indeed, a meta-analysis conducted recently by Durlak et al. (2011) offers strong evidence of the success of SEL programs within schools, as improvements in academic achievement, social competencies, and emotional functioning of students are evidenced. Such programs typically include exercises aimed at promoting empathy, perspective-taking, and conflict resolution ability, all of which are linked to the generation of socially responsible behavior. Cultivation of social and emotional values is therefore not a peripheral requirement of education but a core part of comprehensive development.

Personal Ethics and Responsibility

Honesty, integrity, discipline, and responsibility were frequently cited by respondents, with 6 out of 28 (21%) identifying these as fundamental values they acquired at SPUS. Ethical education plays a vital role in shaping individuals who contribute positively to

society (Rest et al., 1999). One respondent shared, *"To be honest in everything I do and implement what I learned outside the campus,"* while another emphasized, *"Being mindful of my actions and taking responsibility for them."* These reflections suggest that SPUS has successfully instilled ethical awareness in its students, preparing them to act with integrity in both their personal and professional lives. Moral development theories argue that individuals who are taught personal responsibility and integrity in their formative years are more likely to make ethical choices in adulthood (Kohlberg, 1984).

The ethical learning component in development is imperative. Theories of moral development suggest that early childhood years are vital to forming ethical character (Kohlberg, 1984). Those who learn the value of personal responsibility and integrity at a young age will most likely act ethically later in life. Research in moral education validates this argument. For instance, Berkowitz and Bier (2005) conducted a meta-analysis and determined that institutions that actively encourage moral reasoning and character growth among children and youths are successful in promoting ethical behavior as well as preventing cases of delinquency. This highlights the significance of institutions such as SPUS not just to provide knowledge but also to facilitate the ethical growth of their students.

In addition, one should also recognize the influence of context on making ethical decisions. Although individual ethics serve as a general guideline, people have to resolve sophisticated ethical issues in different professional and social environments. Discussing ethical issues from particular spheres of activity emphasizes the necessity for ongoing education and reflective thinking. For example, in a study conducted by Gaudelli (2016), the ethical role of global educators in enhancing social justice and equity is discussed. Such research emphasizes the need for ethical consciousness in dealing with inequalities within a system and fighting for positive social change.

In summary, the focus on honesty, integrity, discipline, and responsibility at SPUS is in line with larger ethical systems that foster responsible citizenship and community welfare. These values are not abstractions but pragmatic instruments that inform personal behavior and professional choice. The insights expressed by SPUS students illustrate the power of ethical education to transform.

Leadership & Interpersonal Skills

Five out of 28 respondents (18%) highlighted leadership, teamwork, and communication skills as essential values acquired during their time at SPUS. Leadership education is increasingly recognized as a critical component of holistic learning, equipping students with the ability to influence and inspire others (Northouse, 2021). One graduate stated, *"I learned to be a communicator and team player,"* while another emphasized, *"Developing leadership skills and working well with others."* These responses demonstrate the importance of fostering leadership abilities within educational settings, as research suggests that strong interpersonal skills enhance problem-solving capabilities and prepare individuals for collaborative work environments (Bolman & Deal, 2017). SPUS's emphasis on leadership development aligns with the notion that education should empower students to take initiative and positively contribute to their communities (Bass, 1990).

Learning leadership skills enables students to initiate change, inspire others, and bring about good into the world. Recent research highlights the advantages of infusing leadership principles in different academic fields. For instance, a study by Komives et al. (2009) indicated that leadership identity development was a complex process that was shaped by personal experiences, interactions with groups, and societal

environments. In addition, studies indicate that leadership development can improve the self-efficacy, critical thinking, and ethical decision-making capabilities of students (Dugan & Komives, 2010). These results support the general impact of leadership development on students' professional and personal development

Academic & Professional Excellence

Lastly, academic and professional excellence was identified as a key theme by 3 out of 28 respondents (11%). This category encompasses hard work, dedication, and alignment with the institution's Vision and Mission. Research highlights that educational institutions play a significant role in cultivating perseverance and a strong work ethic among students (Duckworth et al., 2007). One graduate reflected, "*Hard work and dedication to learning*," while another noted, "*The Vision, Mission, and Quality Policy of SPUS have guided me*." These statements indicate that SPUS effectively promotes a culture of excellence, ensuring that students strive for continuous improvement and success. The integration of institutional values into education helps reinforce motivation and goal-setting behaviors, both of which are crucial for long-term academic and professional achievements (Dweck, 2006).

The other cited graduate's statement – "*The Vision, Mission, and Quality Policy of SPUS have guided me*" – illuminates the significance of integrating personal goals with the institution's vision and mission. When students find their learning experience significant and in accordance with their values, they are more likely to be motivated and committed to achieving success (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Institutions that clearly communicate their values and incorporate them in the curriculum instill a sense of belonging and purpose, which then encourages motivation and goal-setting tendencies.

Current literature supports the influence of institutional values. Shin & Keisler's (2023) study investigated the influence of organizational culture on employee performance and job satisfaction and reported that strong consistency between individual and organizational values played an important role in enhancing job satisfaction and productivity. Though this study is concerned with the workplace, the same principle is applicable to education: when students are engaged in the mission and values of the institution, they are more inclined to devote time and energy to learning. In addition, Aisha's (2025) research highlights the significance of institutions working to create a culture of inclusiveness and belonging since this helps in instilling in students the sense of purpose as well as their desire to excel academically.

Although the early data are a limited subset of graduates, the narrative of academic and professional excellence fueled by hard work, commitment, and adherence to institutional values rings true with wider research. Fostering a culture of excellence demands an approach that involves multiple aspects and includes: instilling in students the confidence in their capacity to learn and improve through effort and commitment, empowering students with persistence and passion for long-term achievements, making sure that students learn and accept the vision and mission of the institution, instilling a sense of belonging and purpose, and instilling an environment where every student feels valued and supported in academic excellence.

Aligning Themes with Paulinian Core Values

After identifying themes, they were aligned with the Paulinian Core Values to examine how the graduates' acquired values reflect the institution's guiding principles.

Table 3. Alignment of Themes with Paulinian Core Values

Paulinian Core Values	Aligned Theme(s)	Explanation
Christ-Centeredness	Faith-Based Values	Graduates emphasized their strong faith, aligning with SPUS's goal of forming Christ-Centered individuals.
Commission	Leadership & Interpersonal Skills, Academic & Professional Excellence	The graduates' focus on leadership, problem-solving, and vision-mission awareness aligns with their sense of purpose in making a positive impact on society.
Community	Social & Emotional Values, Leadership & Interpersonal Skills	Many respondents highlighted teamwork, respect, and responsibility, which contribute to community building.
Charism	Academic & Professional Excellence, Leadership & Interpersonal Skills	The commitment to developing talents, striving for growth, and excelling in various aspects of life mirrors this core value.
Charity	Social & Emotional Values, Personal Ethics & Responsibility	Compassion, empathy, honesty, and responsibility reflect the Paulinian call to serve others, particularly the underprivileged.

The alignment of the themes with Paulinian Core Values confirms that SPUS successfully instills these principles in its graduates. The data shows that students internalized these values and applied them in their lives, reinforcing SPUS's role in holistic education.

Christ-Centeredness emerged as the dominant theme, showing that students deeply value their faith and moral grounding.

Social and Emotional Values, Leadership, and Personal Ethics were also significant, reflecting how SPUS not only nurtures faith but also fosters interpersonal, ethical, and leadership skills.

The Commission and Charism values indicate that students see their education as a preparation for leadership and service, aligning with SPUS's mission to develop proactive, service-oriented graduates.

Christ-Centeredness and Faith-Based Values

Christ-Centeredness is at the core of the Paulinian educational philosophy, which stresses the importance of spirituality and faith in the integrated formation of the person. This value calls for the establishment of one's life on Christian beliefs and their practice through actions. In the accounts of graduates, a strong focus on faith values—such as *prayer, spirituality, and service*—was a dominant theme during their stay at the university. Literature indicates that Christian education instills strong spiritual foundations that inform the moral and ethical outlook of students (Campbell & Tsuruda, 2017; Manea, 2014). The personal testimonies of the graduates confirm that St. Paul University Surigao was able to instill Christ-centered values in them that prepared them for living lives not only academically focused but spiritually directed as well. The integration of *Christ-Centeredness with faith-based values* represents how graduates bring their religious beliefs into both their personal and professional lives, demonstrating that faith-based education has the potential to shape individuals' perspectives forever (Perry, 2007; Glanzer & Ream, 2009).

Commission and Leadership & Interpersonal Skills, Academic & Professional Excellence

The Commission value prioritizes the role of individuals to serve society and make a positive contribution to the common good. It is this sense of purpose that was emphasized by graduates looking back on their leadership missions and a desire to bring about positive change. Their emphasis on academic excellence and leadership follows the central value of Commission, which implies that what they learned in the university provided them with the technical expertise as well as the leadership competencies to bring change. Such topics resonate with existing literature on higher education's contributions to the building of civic professional students (Sequeira et al., 2017; Astin & Sax, 1998). Graduates' positive reporting about strong interpersonal skills and problem-solving abilities further prove the way St. Paul University Surigao (SPUS) encourages a framework where students gain confidence to act in positions of responsibility and sway (Sax, 2004; Cam & Alkal, 2020). This alignment supports the mission of education in promoting socially responsible leaders who are well-equipped to add to the good of others (Bok, 2006; Cauthen, 2016).

Community and Social & Emotional Values, Leadership & Interpersonal Skills

The Community value in the Paulinian tradition emphasizes developing supportive relationships and building a sense of belonging. Graduates all reflected on the ways in which their experience at the university reinforced the importance of teamwork, respect, and responsibility toward others. These comments conform with the idea that universities have an important role to play in fostering emotional intelligence and interpersonal skills that are essential for creating robust communities (Goleman, 1995; *University of Phoenix College of Doctoral Studies Releases White Paper on Aligning Emotional Intelligence Components to Enhance Building of Social Capital*, n.d.). Graduates stated that their professional and academic lives were influenced by their capacity to work in collaboration, value different viewpoints, and undertake collective endeavors. The congruence of *Community with Social and Emotional Values* shows how St. Paul University Surigao (SPUS) cultivates the capacity of students to form and maintain strong relationships, which in turn supports both personal well-being and social cohesion (Boyatzis, 1982; Korpershoek et al., 2019).

Charism and Academic & Professional Excellence, Leadership & Interpersonal Skills

Charism, meaning the special talents and gifts which every person is encouraged to pursue for the good of others, was a recurrent theme among the graduates. Numerous graduates looked at how the university assisted them to nurture their talents, both on an academic level and as a person, making them competent enough to be winners in their individual fields. Such strengths, such as leadership and people skills, tie in exactly with the Charism value of servicing others through excellence. Talent development literature indicates that institutions that seek to develop the strengths and leadership potential of their students prepare the graduates to play a meaningful role in their community (Clifton & Harter, 2003; Balaraman et al., 2024). In promoting a culture of academic excellence and leadership, St. Paul University Surigao (SPUS) inspires students to direct their personal talents toward the service of society, thereby expressing the value of Charism in its mission of education (Sullivan & Rosin, 2008; Hatcher & Studer, 2014).

Charity and Social & Emotional Values, Personal Ethics & Responsibility

The Paulinian value of Charity is a call to a steadfast commitment to the service of others, especially the poor. Graduates also considered their feelings of *social justice*, *compassion*, and *ethical responsibility*, which were central to their university education. This congruence with *Charity* was seen in their participation in volunteerism and community service, which frequently resulted from a strong feeling of personal responsibility to assist others. In fact, values-based education research confirms that building empathy and ethical behavior among students equips them for ethical leadership and responsible citizenship (Hartsough, 2003; Pakizekho & Barkhordari-Sharifabad, 2022). Social and emotional values themes indicate how St. Paul University Surigao senior high school graduates apply the value of Charity in their daily lives, manifesting their commitment to enhancing the well-being of others, particularly the less privileged. This focus on charity resonates with the educational objective of producing students who are both academically qualified and morally accountable (Noddings, 2005; Bergman, 2004).

Conclusions

This research explored the values acquired by Batch 2024 senior high school graduates of St. Paul University Surigao (SPUS) using Thematic Analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The results showed that Christ-Centeredness was the most dominant value indicating SPUS's strong faith-based education. Other significant themes were social and emotional values (compassion, charity, and respect), personal ethics and responsibility (honesty, integrity, and discipline), leadership and interpersonal skills (communication, teamwork, and problem-solving), and academic and professional excellence (hard work, dedication, and alignment with the institution's Vision and Mission). These values resonated with the Paulinian Core Values, proving that SPUS has effectively imbibed moral and ethical ideals in its graduates.

The research points to the integrative impact of Catholic education on the character, leadership, and moral decision-making of students. The findings reveal that SPUS fosters not just academic achievement but also personal growth and a strong sense of moral obligation, enabling graduates to be compassionate, principled, and socially responsible individuals. The responses of the graduates show that values education in SPUS is internalized and applied outside the classroom, shaping their relationships and goals forming them as empowered Paulinians making a difference for Church and society.

Implication

The findings of this study reinforce the critical role of values education in faith-based institutions in preparing students for ethical and socially responsible citizenship. The alignment between the graduates' responses and the Paulinian Core Values suggests that Catholic education can effectively instill long-term moral and spiritual development. Furthermore, the study underscores the importance of experiential learning, mentorship, and institutional mission-driven programs in strengthening students' internalization of values. Future research may explore how these values evolve over time as graduates transition into higher education and professional life.

Limitations

The research is limited to a single institution and interprets findings rather than being statistical. The findings are prone to individual biases and recall bias, and the research does not measure external factors, including family or social settings, that could have played a role in values formation. Despite these limitations, this study offers valuable insights into the influence of Catholic education on moral character, providing recommendations to enhance values education programs in religious institutions.

Recommendation

To further enhance values formation at SPUS, it is recommended that the institution integrate more experiential learning opportunities, such as service-learning projects, leadership workshops, and faith-based outreach programs, that allow students to actively apply their values in real-world settings. Additionally, regular follow-up studies with alumni can help assess the long-term impact of values education and provide insights for continuous program improvement. Lastly, strengthening ethics and leadership training across academic disciplines can further reinforce character formation, ensuring that SPUS graduates continue to uphold and exemplify Christ-Centeredness, compassion, integrity, and social responsibility throughout their lives.

Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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